

REVIEW CERTIFICATE

Pak J Surg Med is delighted to Certify

**Dr Muhammad
Hamid Ch**

for carrying out a thorough critical review of manuscript titled "Cytokine Storm Syndrome, a hidden cause of death in COVID-19 patients?"

Pak J Surg Med is thankful for a meticulous through peer review and it's our pleasure to have you on the peer review board.

Date of Review: May 29, 2020

Certificate Issued: August 03, 2020

Ammar Anwer

Chief Editor

Pak J Surg Med

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